

RISK ASSESSMENT OF PHARMACEUTICAL SUPPLY CHAIN: A MULTI-METHOD EXPLORATION

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ABSTRACT

In an era where pharmaceutical supply chains (PSCs) face heightening complexities and vulnerabilities, this study employs an innovative, multi-method approach to comprehensively assess risks within the pharmaceutical industry. By integrating thematic analysis, the Delphi technique, total interpretive structural modeling (TISM), and fuzzy cross-impact matrix multiplication (MICMAC), the research explores seven risk categories and twenty significant factors, with sixteen pivotal risks distilled through the Delphi technique. TISM establishes interrelationships, while fuzzy MICMAC categorizes risks based on interdependence and driving power. Key findings underscore global health crises and unstable political and economic conditions as primary drivers, capable of significantly disrupting pharmaceutical supply chain flows. This study addresses a critical research gap by emphasizing the interrelationships among different risk categories. Its uniqueness lies in utilizing TISM to craft a pharmaceutical supply chain framework that not only acknowledges interactions but also reveals hidden relationships among risk variables, suggesting potential improvements in pharmaceutical supply chain operations. The new framework aims to enhance processes, streamline resource allocation, and deepen our understanding of how the supply chain functions. The research is uniquely characterized by its empirical exploration of pharmaceutical supply chain risks within three provinces of Pakistan over a year. The inclusion of the TISM framework, Fuzzy MICMAC analysis, and driving dependence graphs adds a layer of novelty to the study's contribution.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical supply chain, Risk Management, Risk Assessment, Thematic analysis, TISM, Fuzzy MICMAC.

INTRODUCTION

Effective supply chain management is recognized as a critical determinant for the success of organizations, particularly in today's rapidly changing and competitive business environment (Singh & Benyoucef, 2013). A wide range of risks could affect each component of the supply chain, and these risks could significantly influence the business's short- and long-term profitability. The risks of critical events in the supply chain network refer to the probability and consequences of unforeseen occurrences or circumstances at the

macro and/or micro level that negatively affect any aspect of a supply chain and result in irregularities or failures at the tactical, strategic, or operational levels (Ho et al., 2015).

The provision of medications is one of the highest priorities in developing countries. Consequently, it is essential to manage the PSC effectively (Jaberidoost et al., 2013). To benefit all stakeholders, an effective PSC provides medicines to patients in the appropriate quantity, with acceptable quality, at the appropriate time,

and at the best price (Lobaugh et al., 2017). A key element of the health system is the PSC, which entails all processes, data, assets, and participants, including manufacturers, suppliers, intermediaries, third-party service providers, logistics operations, marketing and sales activities, and financial and IT operations (Jaberidoost et al., 2013). More than 700 pharmaceutical companies in Pakistan, which has 215 million consumers, are well-positioned to take advantage of opportunities created by these shifting global patterns of supply and demand (Ahmed & Chandani, 2020). In this context, any risks to the pharmaceutical business could have an impact on the efficiency of the healthcare system and disrupt medicine supplies (Craighead & Blackhurst, 2007). To develop best practices for appropriate configuration and adaptability in the pharmaceutical industry, it is crucial to identify and categorize risks throughout the supply chain process (Jaberidoost et al., 2013). According to (Govindan et al., 2015) improving operational performance is possible when supply chain structure and managerial solutions are consistent, as this alignment enhances the organization's ability to identify and mitigate risks effectively, ultimately contributing to more robust risk management practices. However, the primary aim of this research is to identify the influence of critical risk factors on the performance of PSCs. By investigating the relationships among these identified risk elements, our objective is to unveil potential interconnections within the PSC. Furthermore, we intend to highlight the specific critical risks that exert the most detrimental impact on the overall performance of the PSC. Our goal in pursuing this objective is to make a valuable contribution to the improvement of PSC practices in Pakistan, ultimately resulting in greater success and efficiency. Thus, three research questions are formulated. (1) What are the major risk categories and essential critical risk factors in the PSC? (2) How are the identified critical risk factors interrelated? (3) What are the critical risks most adversely influencing the PSC? By addressing these research questions, this study offers valuable insights into risk identification, classification, and factor analysis within the PSC. Initially, this study enhances the risk management discourse within the PSC by presenting a systematic guide for both academics

and practitioners. This guide facilitates the identification, categorization, and analysis of risks specific to the PSC context. Furthermore, it assists practitioners in the PSC in devising effective strategies to address and mitigate risks based on their classification and interconnections. Lastly, the findings offer valuable insights that enable PSC professionals to make informed risk management decisions, contributing to the overall resilience and security of the PSC.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a review of existing literature on the PSC, highlighting research gaps. Following that, section 3 discussed the research methodology. Section 4 details the process of data collection, with subsequent section 5 focusing on data analysis and findings. Sections 6 and 7 are dedicated to discussion and contributions, respectively. The paper concludes by drawing conclusions and proposing future research directions in section 8.

Literature Review:

The common expression of risk is often represented as the product of the probability of occurrence of a particular risk and its potential impact or consequence (Dong & Cooper, 2016; Manuj & Mentzer, 2008). Risks related to the Supply chain are events that disturb or disrupt the flow of materials, information, or funds within the supply chain and halt operations (Ghadge et al., 2012; Tummala & Schoenherr, 2011). Generally, risks are inherent in all business activities (H. Pfohl et al., 2011) but PSCs are more likely to face difficulties because of their unique perishability that they lose their usefulness after a specific expiration date (Perlman & Levner, 2014). To uphold the quality and other performance criteria, supply chain coordinators need to efficiently and effectively coordinate management tasks (Moazzam et al., 2018). However, this is a challenging task as threats can originate from a variety of sources. For example, because of contamination, defective and unsafe products might be recalled, and such recalls would be costly and bad for businesses' reputations and service levels (Maruchek et al., 2011). Before the consumption of the finished products, risks could appear simultaneously in many supply chain stages like manufacturing, storage, processing, and distribution (Nakandala

et al., 2017) with adverse and significant effects on the effectiveness of the supply chain (Blackhurst et al., 2005; Macdonald et al., 2018; Yang & Yang, 2010). There are specific dangers related to pharmaceutical products' quality and safety during processing, the most significant potential danger to pharmaceutical safety is contamination, such as radioactive drugs which can involve events that could lead to a public health emergency of concern on a national or international scale (Pullirsch et al., 2014). Further, the PSC faces challenges because it's complex. It involves many steps, from making drugs to getting them to patients. Lots of people handle the products, and sometimes mistakes happen. Fixing these mistakes can cost a lot of money. Also, there are many rules and regulations to follow, which makes it even more challenging for the pharmaceutical industry to overcome these problems (Markarian, 2015). Therefore, creating a typology with a systematic and comprehensive collection of risks is essential for effective risk analysis and management.

Several definitions of supply chain critical risk are provided in the literature (Bogataj & Bogataj, 2007; Wagner & Bode, 2006) most concentrate on particular functions (Jüttner et al., 2003) or a specific element of the supply chain and do not consider the whole chain (Ellis et al., 2010; Zsidisin, 2003). This research study will use the definition of supply chain risk suggested by Ho et al., (2015) 'the probability and effects of unforeseen macro or micro level events or situations that negatively affect any aspect of a supply chain and cause tactical, operational or strategic level anomalies or failure'. Supply chain potential risks can be categorized based on several prospective (Rangel et al., 2015). Such as internal and external risks as well as risks with low/high probabilities and high/low consequences (Kumar et al., 2010). Moreover, several research studies have categorized risks into three groups, internal organizational risk, demand and supply network risk and external environmental risk (Christopher & Lee, 2004; Lin & Zhou, 2011). Further risks are categorized into process and control risks (Turner et al., 2022); war and terrorism risks (Akter et al., 2022); political instability (Baldwin & Freeman, 2022); natural disaster risks (Sodhi et al., 2023); information, financial and transportation risk (M. Wang & Jie, 2020). All of these risks are relevant to the PSC,

but operational and the risk related to disruption of supply/demand are particularly important (Behzadi et al., 2018).

To evaluate, manage, and reduce the detrimental consequences of PSC risks, a variety of quantitative and qualitative research techniques are used including bibliometric and network analysis (Fahimnia et al., 2015), centralized decision model with CVAR (Xie et al., 2023), fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (FAHP) (Dua et al., 2023) and interpretive structural modelling (ISM) (Khan et al., 2024). All these techniques have benefits for analyzing PSC risks, but they also each have drawbacks.

For instance, (AHP) is unable to evaluate risk and uncertainty properly because it assumes that risk is relatively important (Chan & Kumar, 2007). While ISM can answer the "what" and "how" questions in theory building, it cannot address the "why" (Jena et al., 2017). It's interesting to note that despite TISM's advantage over ISM in explaining why question has been used in several contexts such as construction (Sandbhor & Botre, 2014), smartphone manufacturing ecosystems (Jena et al., 2016), cloud computing (Radhika & Pramod, 2014) and flexible manufacturing systems (Jain & Raj, 2015). The interrelationships between various PSC concerns have not yet been identified in any pharmaceutical sector studies using TISM. Qualitative approaches are mostly utilized for categorizing risks and developing SCRM concepts (Cutter, 2016). Whereas, for risk assessment, quantitative methodologies are applied (Fahimnia et al., 2015).

Based on the examination of the literature, we discovered several research gaps that open up opportunities for future research:

First, Pakistan presents a unique and markedly different context for the supply chain (Congress et al., 2011). Unlike developed Western countries where supply chain structures are developed, poorly developed supply chain mechanisms pose difficulties in risk identification, correlation (Paul et al., 2021) and thereby mitigation strategies (Can Saglam, 2021). Second, (Ho et al., 2015) literature review revealed that only six out of 90 studies considered PSC risks. This presents a prime opportunity for researchers to search deeper and identify sector-specific risk factors in the pharmaceutical domain. Third, most of the efforts done to date

have been devoted to the identification, analysis, mitigation and assessment of critical risk. Currently, the research does not adequately address the interdependencies and interrelationships among different risk categories. (Ho et al., 2015). While, the hidden impacts of one risk related to another risk may cause significant harm to PSCs, there is a need for more research to explore the relationships between different PSC risks (ManMohan S. Sodhi, 2004). Finally, the TISM technique has not yet been employed in a study to create a PSC framework that takes into consideration the interactions between different PSC risk variables. To the best of my knowledge, this work is the first to characterize the interconnections between different PSC risks using TISM.

Bridging research gaps, this study delves into interconnections among PSC risks through rigorous methods and diverse data from three Pakistani provinces over a year. Its unique empirical exploration significantly enhances existing knowledge, paving the way for addressing crucial research needs.

Research methodology:

This research adopts interpretivism to fully comprehend the event and its complexity within its specific context (Ishtiaq, 2019) by accepting the divergent perspectives of various people from various groups (Saunders et al., 2015). Therefore, while looking at complex problems and managerial realities, interpretivism is better suited than other research philosophies. Considering that a PSC is a complex system of connected, cooperative entities (Dani, 2015), its primary objective is to ensure the accessibility of medications to consumers (Prinja et al., 2015). A comprehensive understanding of risks within the PSC necessitates an exploration of the beliefs, values, biases, attitudes, sentiments, and perspectives of PSC practitioners (Morehouse, 2012). Therefore, an interpretivist research paradigm is deemed suitable for this study. Moreover, Researchers believe that interpretivism and inductive logic are inextricably linked (Silverman, 2021; Willis, 2007). Quantitative techniques are largely deductive,

whereas qualitative techniques are inductive. By utilizing a variety of data collection methodologies and analysis procedures, qualitative research has been recognized as an effective method for examining participants' meanings and how they relate to one another (Saunders et al., 2015). While quantitative research has been successful in verifying objective hypotheses by analyzing the relationship between variables (Ishtiaq, 2019). Thus, it is challenging to capture such perspectives using quantitative methods, a qualitative strategy, as opposed to a quantitative one, is employed in this study to collect the PSC experts' opinions on the PSC risks, comprehend how these risks influence one another, and identify the key risks. The whole research methodology framework for this study is depicted in Figure 1.

Methods of data collection

The most popular interviewing method for gathering empirical data is the semi-structured interview, especially for complicated or open-ended studies and questions (Adeoye-Olatunde & Olenik, 2021). As it also reveals previously undiscovered information (O'Keeffe et al., 2016). Moreover, when interviewees are given enough chances to talk freely, new facts or knowledge might come to light (Langley & Meziani, 2020). In comparison to other interviewing formats like structured and unstructured interviews, the semi-structured interview is better adapted to the examination of respondents' perspectives and opinions about complicated and occasionally sensitive themes. Additionally, it permits the researcher to inquire further to clarify responses and get additional data (Bellardita et al., 2021). Thus, the semi-structured interview method will be used in this study to gather views and opinions from PSC managers on PSC risks. Before developing an interview, guide and gathering empirical data, a review of the literature on PSC risk identification, classification, assessment, and mitigation will be carried out to get accurate and comprehensive data during the interviews and to gain an understanding of the topic domain under investigation.

Fig 1: Research method adopted

Methods of data analysis:

After collecting empirical data by using semi-structured interviews, which will thereafter be examined by combining the thematic analysis, Delphi approach, TISM, along fuzzy MICMAC analysis. The studies will use multiple data analysis allowing to exploration of many interpretations of a single dataset (Clarke et al., 2015) as well as to weigh the advantages and drawbacks of individual approaches against one another (Frost et al., 2011). In many academic fields, such as psychology, sociology, and other social sciences, thematic analysis is a common technique for studying qualitative data. It entails finding, examining, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis is designed to provide researchers with a structured and systematic approach to conducting qualitative analysis independently and reliably (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). Furthermore, it offers three clear benefits: It can show similarities and variations across different data sets, summarize significant elements of a huge amount of data with minimal description and produce unexpected discoveries

(Braun & Clarke, 2006). Thematic analysis, in contrast to other qualitative data analysis techniques like conversational analysis and discourse analysis, is a simple and straightforward technique that does not require theoretical subtleties and specialized knowledge (Javadi & Zarea, 2016). Thus, to identify risk themes, thematic analysis was used as the initial data analysis technique. In addition, a Delphi technique was used to validate the PSC risks in which a team of ten experts from pertinent fields were assembled to choose the most salient risks. The primary reason for using the Delphi technique in decision-making is to gather data in a structured way when the only other option might be relying on personal stories or entirely subjective opinion (Barrios et al., 2021). Next, TISM will be utilized to create links between the identified PSC risks since it is a useful method for determining interactions between various factors and the strength of their associations (Jayalakshmi & Pramod, 2015). Yadav (2014) suggested that TISM is a well-established technique and has been utilized widely in a variety of circumstances for

establishing relationships between various aspects. ISM, or interpretive structural modelling, is the technique that gave rise to TISM. ISM and TISM can both identify the interrelationships between the variables that are being examined; however, in ISM, the interpretation of direct links is generally weak and may not accurately reflect the complete decision-making process (Jena et al., 2017). Determining the interdependence among the elements can be applied by using additional techniques like SEM (Structural Equation Modelling), DEMATEL (Decision Making Trial and Evaluation Laboratory), ANP (Analytic Network Process) and graph theory, however, they cannot be used in this study due to their limitations. For example, due to the complicated technique involved in ANP, its usefulness is limited, and SEM requires a sizable sample size (Mangla et al., 2018). DEMATEL has difficulties addressing issues with uncertainty and the bias inherent in human assessment (Si et al., 2018) and the ability of graph theory to predict the direction of links between variables is restricted (B. Wang et al., 2020). Thus, TISM will be used to convert ill-articulated mental models into well-organized forms. As a result, it helped resolve all the theory-related queries (N. Yadav, 2014).

Finally, the TISM model of PSC risks will be validated by using the fuzzy cross-impact matrix multiplication MICMAC analysis to identify the main risks in various categories depending on the effect of the risks. Initially, the MICMAC analysis will develop to look at binary connections between various factors, then the fuzzy set theory will be used as an extra input of the potential of interaction among the elements to boost the sensitivity of the MICMAC analysis (Bhosale & Kant, 2016). G. Yadav and Desai, (2017) suggested that when a significant number of items are included for analysis, the incorporation of fuzzy set theory in TISM-MICMAC can be useful. Although alternative techniques like the Interpretive Ranking Process (IRP) and the Analytic Hierarchical Process (AHP) can help in identifying the relative importance of elements, they either fall short in the area of consistency in experts' opinions or have limited relevance for pairwise matrices larger than 9 x 9 (Mangla et al., 2018). Thus the fuzzy MICMAC will be used as it can evaluate each element's significance by taking into account the strength of the

relationships between them (Bhosale and Kant 2016).

Empirical data collection:

This research gathered empirical data from professionals involved in PSC risk management. Data on PSC risks were gathered through a semi-structured interview. To find relevant participants for this study, purposive and snowball sampling were used (Saunders et al., 2015). Initially, purposive sampling was used to locate appropriate individuals who were deemed to be educated about PSC risks. Criteria for selecting appropriate individuals will: (1) the participants must be a part of the pharmaceutical industry and will be actively engaged in PSC risk management; (2) To ensure a high level of expertise and knowledge, the participant must have more than 7 years of relevant professional experience in PSC risk management; (3) The chosen company must be either medium-sized (with between 10 and 249 employees) or large-sized (with more than 249 employees). Since these businesses have extensive experience and knowledge of PSC risk management. Afterwards, additional volunteers will be found through snowball sampling.

Francis et al., (2010) made the recommendation advocating the necessity of conducting a minimum of 10 interviews during the preliminary sample analysis phase. By this guideline, the initial phase involved the purposeful selection of 10 participants through a purposive sampling technique. Commencing the data collection process, we engaged with a pharmaceutical company situated in the Punjab province of Pakistan. These companies specialize in the handling of high-risk, temperature-sensitive radioactive oncological medicines, and boast strong affiliations with local upstream and downstream partners. Subsequently, the employment of a snowball sampling method facilitated the identification of supplementary participants.

Adhering to the predefined criteria for participant recruitment, certain enterprises were deemed unsuitable for inclusion in this study. Consequently, a total of only three potential organizations met the selection criteria. Undertaking an additional round of three interviews was a deliberate step to validate the saturation of data. However, the outcomes of

these interviews reinforced the findings from the initial set, with no notable emergence of novel themes or perspectives. This served as a clear indicator that the information obtained had reached a point of saturation, meaning that further interviews were unlikely to contribute significantly to the depth or breadth of the data. As a result of this careful consideration and acknowledgement of data saturation, the decision was made to conclude the interview phase, resulting in a final sample size of 13 participants. This approach ensures the integrity

of the study by providing a comprehensive understanding of the chosen research topics without unnecessary repetition or redundancy in participant responses.

Comprehensive details about each interviewee are presented in Table 1. This tabulation encompasses specifics such as the geographical location of the interviewees, their respective roles and positions within their companies, as well as the responsibilities these companies undertake within the realm of the PSC.

Table 1: Interview information

Province	Company	Interviewees Designation	Role/Job description/Total experience
Punjab	A	Company owner	Import/Export of Oncology medicine, supply medicine to hospitals and distributors. (15 years)
	B	Logistic officer	Providing the supply chain needs and requirements , consuming and ordering of medicine/equipment. (08 years)
	C	Manager	Wholesalers , ensure the timely, efficient, and safe provision of the necessary drugs. (10 years)
	D	Director	Distributor and wholesaler , purchasing, storing, selling and distributing of medicine. (12 years)
Khyber Pakhtunkhwa	A	Manager Material Management	Controls production, inventory, transporting, receiving, and the storage of goods , sales forecasting, maintaining inventory, production planning and scheduling. (09 years)
	B	Sales Executives	Demonstrating, Promoting and presenting products , maintaining correct data, participating in trade shows, conferences, meetings, and evaluating sales performance. (08 years)
	C	Senior Pharmacist	Patient counselling and monitoring of drugs , maintaining temperature of cool chain drugs, procurement. (13 years)
	D	Owner/Director	Manufacturing and distributing , providing guidance research and development; communication; and preserving relationships with the pharmaceutical industry. (15 years)
	E	Manager Procurement	Sourcing, negotiation, managing contracts, and managing supplier relationships , Developing a purchase strategy, examining and processing purchase orders, and dealing with suppliers to negotiate rates and contracts. (09 years)
Sindh	A	General Manager	Oversee all daily operations ,

		Managing staff, correct dispensing of drugs, keeping an eye on inventory levels, and adhering to all relevant rules and regulations. (08 years)
B	Project Manager	Coordination and operation , identification and mitigation of risks, monitoring overall project activities, arranging training, seminars and providing relevant information. (08 years)
C	Manager Marketing	Sales/marketing , Create marketing campaigns and revenue strategies. Keep tabs on sales activity and statistics. Sell and promote the company's goods and services. (13 years)
D	Supply chain and Logistics officer	Planning, logistics operations, ordering , Sourcing and procuring all supplies and services, inventory management, and warehousing. (08 years)

The thorough analysis of risks was facilitated through interviews conducted with PSC experts, owners, directors, and sales executives within the pharmaceutical sector. Participants were allowed to expound on specific risks, challenges, and the strategies employed to mitigate these risks. A printed version of the interview outline was provided to the participants five days in advance, allowing them to familiarize themselves with the topics to be covered. Each interview, lasting approximately 50 to 70 minutes, encouraged participants to freely express their thoughts on the posed questions, aiming to stimulate the discovery of innovative ideas.

Data Analysis and Findings:

In this section, we illustrate the process of thematically analyzing diverse content derived from semi-structured interviews, leading to the identification of various themes representing risks. Additionally, the Delphi technique is applied to discern the most significant Psychological Safety Culture (PSC) risks. The TISM approach is employed to model the interrelationships among the identified PSC risks. Subsequently, the fuzzy MICMAC approach is utilized to assess the driving and dependent power of PSC risks, facilitating the identification of principal risks.

Risk (themes) identified through thematic analysis:

Thematic analysis is an approach to qualitative study used to find, examine, and interpret themes or patterns in textual, auditory or visual recordings (Braun & Clarke, 2006). It is frequently used in disciplines like anthropology, sociology, psychology, and other social and behavioral sciences, as well as in several humanities subfields (Nowell et al., 2017). The process of conducting thematic analysis is visually illustrated in Figure 2 through a series of six sequential steps. Familiarizing with collected information, generating preliminary (codes), looking for themes, examining and reviewing themes, naming and defining themes, and creating the final summary report. The first codes were created after carefully reading and editing verbatim transcriptions to ensure that any extraneous information was removed. The pharmaceutical companies who took part in the semi-structured interviews reviewed all the coded data to ensure the correctness of the outcomes from the interviews and the risk notes. Furthermore, we will find themes by analyzing the connections between codes, themes, and primary themes and sub-themes. Once every potential theme, sub-themes, and their associated codes had been generated, all pertinent codes were sorted and arranged into potential themes. Before producing a thematic map, we first determined if the themes were suitable for the entire dataset and the extracted codes. Following

a review of the themes, a continuing analysis was done to make sure that each theme had a clear

name, identity and definition as shown in Appendix 6.

Fig 2: Process of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006)

Source: Authors' own

Appendix 6 provides a comprehensive summary of the empirical findings concerning various categories of risk. It establishes connections between first-order PSC codes extracted directly from interview transcripts (outlined in column one), and second-order PSC risk themes/factors which encapsulate the essence of these first-order PSC codes (elaborated in column two). In column three, the discernment of evidence from each interview case is indicated. The affirmative presence of evidence is denoted by a checkmark (√), whereas the absence of a tick denotes the lack of supporting evidence, (see Appendix 6, column three). Lastly, the amalgamated dimensions unveil the principal PSC risk classifications (refer to the fourth column).

Delphi technique to identify the most salient PSC risks:

Buettner et al., (2020) proposed that employing the Delphi approach is suitable for qualitative

research involving a group of ten to thirty professionals. Following the identification of 20 PSC risks through thematic analysis, the Delphi technique was employed to prioritize the most significant ones. A panel consisting of ten experts from relevant fields was convened to engage in discussions and validate these risks. Through mutual consultations, a consensus was reached, leading to the selection of 16 salient risks as depicted in Table 2 out of the initial 20 PSC risks that pose potential hindrances to the PSC. The remaining four risks were excluded from further consideration. The panel comprises four material management managers representing various hospitals, two supply chain officers from the public sector, two procurement officers, and two company owners associated with the private sector within the pharmaceutical industry of Pakistan.

Table 2: Salient risks

PSC salient risks	Risks codes
Shortage of raw materials and import drugs	R1
Lack of contract management	R2
High energy cost	R3
Lack of skills	R4
Intellectual property theft	R5
Lack of information visibility	R6
Payment sluggishness	R7
Trade disputes	R8
Rapid changes in government policies	R9
Poor planning	R10
Counterfeit medicines	R11
Lack of foreign currency	R12
Fluctuation in price	R13
Unstable political and economic conditions	R14
Global health crises (Pandemic)	R15
Unbalanced supply and demand	R16

Model for risk hierarchy constructed using TISM analysis:

The TISM analysis was processed using the risk components derived from the thematic analysis to provide a risk hierarchal structure that included nine phases, as highlighted in Figure 3.

I. Identify and define Elements:

The TISM analysis was processed using twenty PSC risk variables that were discovered through a

thematic analysis. Additionally, the most salient sixteen risk factors were chosen by 10 PSC experts.

II. Determination of the contextual relationship between elements:

The context-dependent link between two PSC risks is characterized as risk (A) causes risk (B).

Fig 3: TISM analysis process.

Modified from (Zhao et al., 2020)

Define interpretation for contextual relationship:

Based on their nationality, work history, area of specialization, and current roles and responsibilities, the nine experts who participated in the semi-structured interviews were chosen to get their opinions on the Pairwise interpretation and comparison of the relationship between the PSC risk that verifies whether an association "Risk (A) influences/causes Risk (B)" essentially exists or not (Yes or No)

III. Paired comparison of elements to form a knowledge base that considers contextual connections and suitable interpretive logic:

To compare the 16 identified PSC hazards pairwise, an "interpretive logic-knowledge base" was created. The body of knowledge used to implement this research has 156 rows ($16 \times 16 - 16 = 240$) in total.

IV. Transitivity test and Development of reachability matrix:

The interpretive logic-knowledge base served as the foundational framework for the construction of an initial reachability matrix, wherein '1' denoted (YES) relationships and '0' represented (NO) relationships. This matrix is detailed in Appendix 2. Subsequently, rigorous scrutiny for adherence to transitivity rules was conducted, leading to the refinement of the initial reachability matrix into its final form, as presented in Appendix 3. As per the principles of transitivity, when an association exists between element "A" and element "B," and a concurrent association is identified between element "B" and element "C," it logically necessitates the establishment of an association between element "A" and element "C."

V. Determination of Level partitioning on reachability matrix:

According to Singh and Benyoucef, (2013) following a series of iterations, the final reachability matrix created in the preceding stage was partitioned into different levels dependent on each component's reachability and antecedent sets. The level partitioning was continued until the levels of all PSC threats had been identified. (Appendix 1) illustrates how the nine levels (1 to 9) of the 16 PSC risks were divided. A digraph along with a TISM-based hierarchal model was created using the levels that were discovered.

VI. Produce a digraph:

For representation, the 16 PSC supply chain risks were displayed as a digraph in which major transitive linkages were represented by dotted lines and direct Links were built based on the connections shown in the final reachability matrix.

VII. Produce Binary Interaction matrix:

A binary interaction matrix is created from the finished digraph, with every component denoting an interaction. The cells with a single entry are interpreted by choosing the relevant interpretations using the knowledge base in the form of an interpretative matrix (Jain & Raj, 2015).

VIII. Process Total Interpretive Structural Model:

The TISM is built using the connection and interpretive information of the interpretative direct interaction matrix with a digraph. The nodes of the digraph are replaced with the interpretation of the objects in the boxes. The interpretation is represented in each cell of the interpretative direct interaction matrix by the side of the relevant links in the structural model. As a result, the structural model is completely interpreted, containing all its nodes and links.

A nine-level TISM model was produced as a result of the TISM analysis of PSC risks as shown in figure 4. It can be perceived that global health crises (pandemic) (R15), unstable political and economic conditions (R14), lack of foreign currency (R12), fluctuation in price (R13), rapid changes in government policies (R9), lack of information visibility (R6) and poor planning (R10) comprise levels 04 to 09 in the model of TISM hierarchy. The shortage of raw materials and import drugs (R1), lack of contract management (R2), and unbalanced supply and demand (R16) are at the 03 level accompanied by payment sluggishness (R7) and Trade disputes (R8) which take up the 02 level. Lastly, high energy cost (R3), lack of skills (R4), intellectual property theft (R5) and counterfeit medicines (R11) occupy the 01 level in the TISM hierarchal model.

In essence, the TISM model underscores that the most significant challenges facing PSC are rooted in global health crises, such as pandemics, and the instability stemming from volatile political and economic conditions. These factors contribute to a dearth of foreign currencies (Karabag, 2020); the devaluation of national currencies (Abuselidze, 2019) and price fluctuations (AlThaqeb & Algharabali, 2019) collectively posing formidable obstacles to the sustainability and success of PSC. This, in turn, directly impacts the public's access to affordable pharmaceuticals (Lucero-Prisno III et al., 2020) and can trigger swift alterations in government policies (Tisdell, 2020). When government policies change suddenly, companies may struggle to promptly adapt to new requirements, potentially leading to compliance issues (Hasthi & Sodhi, 2020). This can affect the tracking and reporting of critical information related to product manufacturing, distribution, and quality

control (Mourtzis, 2020). Additionally, lack of information visibility results in poor planning by putting inaccurate data and assumptions to delayed decisions (Rodríguez-Espindola et al., 2020). Furthermore, poor planning in the supply chain of pharmaceuticals can lead to a lack of effective contract management resulting in various negative consequences including missed contract deadlines, inadequate resource allocation, incomplete and unclear contracts, strained supplier relationships, cost overruns, compliance risks, inventory management issues, limited data visibility, and potential damage to the company's reputation (Famiyeh et al., 2017). To address these challenges, pharmaceutical companies should prioritize robust supply chain planning and establish clear contract management processes to ensure transparency, efficiency, and compliance (Sigalov et al., 2021).

Integration of fuzzy MICMAC: Categorization of PSC risks:

Computing the linkages between two PSC risks as '0' or '1' results in the development of the hierarchy model of TISM. A PSC risk is signified by "0" if there is no association between the two of them, and "1" if there is a relationship. These risks do not, however, always relate in an equal manner. Other relationships might be weak. Some relationships might be strong, some might be considerably strong (D. K. Yadav & Barve, 2016). Instead of just evaluating relationships up to that point, the fuzzy MICMAC analysis was utilized to assess the strength of correlations to improve the study's sensitivity and get around the TISM model's constraints. According to (Rahim et al., 2021) qualitative assessment on a 0–1 scale is used to determine the likelihood of interaction as illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Fuzzy scale

Reachability	
Potential	Values
Unimportant	0
Very Low	0.1
Low	0.3
Medium	0.5
High	0.7
Very high	0.9
Full	1

Source: Authors' own

In terms of relationship strength, greater driving power indicates greater systemic driving and greater dependence power indicates greater systemic dependence. Furthermore, a three-stage process was used to conduct the fuzzy MICMAC analysis.

Binary direct relationship matrix:

The final reachability matrix of PSC hazards has been transformed as a binary direct reachability matrix by converting the diagonal components to zeros and discarding transitivity, see (Appendix 4).

Creating the fuzzy direct relationship matrix:

The application of fuzzy set theory played a crucial role in enhancing the sensitivity of the conventional MICMAC analysis. The conventional analysis solely focuses on binary interactions, which can be limiting. Fuzzy set theory offers a more nuanced approach by allowing for qualitative evaluation on a 0–1 scale. This scale ranges from Unimportant (0) to Very Low (0.1), Low (0.3), Medium (0.5), High (0.7), Very High (0.9), and Full (1) to express the likelihood of interaction. These numerical values were employed to assess the correlation between two risks, as informed by expert insights in the TISM (Total Interpretive Structural Modeling) analysis. To construct a Fuzzy Direct Reachability Matrix (FDRM), these values were incorporated into the binary Direct Reachability Matrix. This methodology enhances the robustness of the research, as it considers not only reachability but also the potential for reachability, a more comprehensive approach than the simplistic reachability consideration used previously.

(Appendix 5) presents the Fuzzy Direct Reachability Matrix for reference FDRM.

Developing of fuzzy MICMAC stabilized matrix:

Following the concept of fuzzy matrix multiplication, as introduced by (Gorane & Kant, 2013) and elaborated upon by (W. B. Vasantha Kandasamy et al., 2007), the initial step of this procedure involves utilizing the FDRM as the foundational framework. Iterative multiplication of this matrix is performed until both the driver power and dependent hierarchies attain stability, characterized by constancy over time. It is worth noting that fuzzy matrix multiplication is fundamentally an extension of Boolean matrix multiplication but within the realm of fuzzy set theory. This implies that the outcome of multiplying two fuzzy matrices yields yet another fuzzy matrix. The attainment of dependence and driving power is achieved by aggregating the entries representing interaction possibilities in the respective columns and rows independently. In essence, the resulting fuzzy set C can be viewed as an amalgamation of fuzzy sets A and B. The multiplication rule governing this process can be succinctly described as follows:

$$C = A \cdot B = \max_k [\min(a_{ik}, b_{kj})] \text{ Where } A = [a_{ik}] \text{ and } B = [b_{kj}]$$

A stabilized matrix, as detailed in Table 5, was generated using MATLAB. This involved computing the matrices through the Boolean matrix multiplication process, specifically by multiplying the final direct reachability matrix with the transpose matrix of the final direct reachability matrix.

Table 5: The fuzzy stabilized MICMAC matrix

	RI	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16	Driving
RI	0	0.3	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0.9
R2	0.3	0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0.3	1.8
R3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R6	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
R7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R9	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
R10	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1.8
R11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3

R12	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0.3	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0.3	2.3
R13	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	2.1
R14	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0	0.3	0.5	0	0.3	0.5	0	0	0	0	0.3	3
R15	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0	0.3	0.5	0	0.3	0.5	0	0	0	0	0.3	3.2
R16	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.7
	2	2	2.6	3.4	2.4	0	2.1	2.2	0	0.6	2.8	0	0	0	0	1.5	

Dependent

The PSC risks are investigated and mapped using MICMAC analysis by the driving and dependent powers. These risks are categorized into four groups using MICMAC analysis: independent, linkage, dependent and autonomous.

a) Independent variables (Risks): The risk variables, which include risks from excessive driving and limited dependency power which comprise lack of information visibility (R6), Rapid changes in government policies (R9), Poor planning (R10), lack of foreign currency (R12), fluctuation in price (R13), unstable political and economic conditions (R14) and global health crises (R15). These risks, which are at the bottom of the TISM hierarchy model, serve as inputs and

important variables for the system and have a significant negative impact on PSC.

b) Linkage variables (Risks): This collection of factors exhibits great driving and dependency power. The system is significantly impacted by a high driving power, whereas a high dependence power is reliant heavily on the system. In this category, Lack of contract management (E2) is the sole risk factor. Any modifications to the procedure will have an impact on this risk factor and provide feedback on the system as a whole. Although this risk may be induced or affected by lower-level hazards in the TISM hierarchy, it also has a major driving force that can affect some other risks.

Fig 5: Fuzzy MICMAC analysis

c) Dependent Variables (Risks): This risk group exhibits significant dependence and weak driving powers. These risks are incredibly reliant on the system's inputs, which means that all other risk variables are necessary for them to have the least amount of impact on PSC. These risks are

shortage of raw materials and import drugs (R1), high energy cost (R3), lack of skills (R4), Intellectual property theft (R5), payment sluggishness (R7), trade disputes (R8) and counterfeit medicines (R11).

d) **Autonomous Variables (Risks):** This category of factors has less dependency and driving force. In this group, there is just one risk factor, and that's Unbalanced supply and demand (E16). The TISM hierarchy structure shows that this risk factor has very few ties to the system and is therefore always cut off from it. It doesn't have a significant impact on the system.

Discussion:

One of the primary goals of this study is to establish a TISM hierarchy for the critical PSC risks and equip managers and policymakers with enough knowledge to mitigate these risks to ensure a sustainable supply chain in the pharmaceutical business. This study employed a methodological approach that combined semi-structured interviews and the Delphi technique to comprehensively investigate the risks associated with PSC processes in Pakistan. The study was conducted over one year and encompassed three provinces: Punjab, Sindh, and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Through rigorous thematic analysis, we identified a total of 20 risk factors about the functioning of the PSC, as detailed in Appendix 6. To refine our focus and pinpoint the most significant PSC risks, we leveraged the Delphi technique. This involved assembling a panel of ten experts, each hailing from the relevant regions and possessing substantial expertise in the subject matter. Their collective insights and evaluations led to the selection of 16 salient PSC risks, shown in Table 2. These findings represent a consolidated and validated set of critical risk factors that merit in-depth consideration within the context of PSC operations.

(Jiang et al., 2019) proposed that the application of MICMAC facilitates the identification of potential risks, enabling organizations to formulate effective risk mitigation strategies and contingency plans for factors that could potentially initiate cascading effects within the system. To enhance the analytical capabilities of MICMAC, fuzzy numbers have been employed, and a fuzzy MICMAC approach has been utilized to assess both driving and dependence power among distinct groups (Issac & Baral, 2020) as illustrated in Figure 5. The findings indicate that pandemics (R15) and unstable political and economic conditions (R14) are the main challenges in PSC with stronger driving forces at the TISM base level. Therefore, to create an

effective and efficient PSC, top management should focus more on these Challenges. In addition, the MICMAC model also depicts that Shortage of raw materials and import drugs (R1), high energy cost (R3), Lack of skills (R4), Intellectual property theft (R5), Payment sluggishness (R7), trade disputes (R8) and counterfeit medicines (R11) has the weak driving powers and establishing the highest level in the TISM hierarchy model. However these risks are heavily dependent on other PSC risks which have strong driving power and weak dependent power on other risks like lack of information visibility (R6), rapid changes in government policies (R9), poor planning (R10), lack of foreign currency (R12), fluctuation in price (R13), unstable political and economic conditions (R14) and global health crises pandemic (R15). Thus, these are the main PSC risks, to overcome them, a company's top management needs to pay more attention to them.

Figure 5 demonstrates that the only risk for linking the driving risks to the dependent risks is a lack of contract management (R2). The absolute dependent risks are produced by the linking risk, which is generated from the absolute driving risks. Finally, Figure 5 depicts that there is just one autonomous risk, Unbalanced Supply and Demand (R16), which is less dependent and driven. This particular risk factor is always isolated from the system because it has minimal connections to it. It doesn't significantly affect the system (Zhao et al., 2020). This result underscores the potential significance of the findings in assisting upper management in their quest to identify and address hurdles in enhancing the PSC. The focal point of our research has been the development of a model designed specifically to scrutinize the challenges within Pakistan's PSC. However, it is worth noting that the applicability of this model extends beyond the pharmaceutical sector; it can be adapted for utilization in diverse business domains. Moreover, the classification framework serves as a valuable tool for elucidating, conveying, and transferring knowledge regarding risks across various departments within the organization. Additionally, it facilitates effective risk management by promoting communication and knowledge exchange not only within the company but also among different partners involved in the PSC. This comprehensive

approach empowers management to effectively navigate and address a wide spectrum of risks, both within the company and from a broader supply chain perspective.

This study provides crucial insights for pharmaceutical industry managers and decision-makers. By identifying seven distinct risk categories and twenty significant factors, the study offers a nuanced understanding of the potential challenges faced by PSCs. Managers can use this information to develop targeted strategies for risk mitigation and operational resilience (Rezapour et al., 2018). The emphasis on global health crises and unstable political and economic conditions as primary drivers underscores the need for proactive measures in preparing for and responding to such disruptions (Bode et al., 2022). The proposed framework, integrating TISM and Fuzzy MICMAC analysis, provides a practical tool for managers to assess and address interrelated risks within the supply chain (Manjunatheshwara & Vinodh, 2018). Implementing the findings can lead to more robust and adaptable supply chain operations, ultimately enhancing the industry's ability to navigate uncertainties effectively.

From an academic standpoint, this research contributes significantly to the field of supply chain management and risk analysis. The innovative multi-method approach, incorporating thematic analysis, the Delphi technique, TISM, and Fuzzy MICMAC analysis, enriches the methodological toolkit available for studying complex systems. The identification of risk categories and factors, along with the empirical exploration in three provinces of Pakistan, adds valuable data to the existing body of knowledge. The study's emphasis on interrelationships among different risk categories fills a critical research gap, providing a holistic view that can inform future studies. The inclusion of driving dependence graphs and the TISM framework adds depth to the academic discourse on supply chain risk management. This research not only expands the theoretical understanding of PSC risks but also sets a model for comprehensive and practical research methodologies in similar contexts.

Contribution of study:

This study makes some important contributions to supply chain managerial procedures. First, it

identifies several risk categories from a PSC perspective, providing practitioners with a broad overview of PSC risks and raising their risk awareness. Unit, (2009) conducted a survey, that indicated that over half of respondents claimed their company substantially underestimates the potential effect of supply chain risk, and more than one-third of respondents thought that generally there is a lack of knowledge of supply chain risk. The findings of this empirical study will assist PSC management in increasing their understanding of potential risks that the PSC may encounter and will allow them to take the required precautions in advance to mitigate or eliminate the risk.

Second, this study investigates the interrelationship between various types of PSC risks. (Ho et al., 2015) suggested that better management can result from investigating the combined impact of different risks rather than focusing on each risk factor separately. By using a logical structure, awareness of PSC risks and their interrelationship will enable PSC managers to effectively prioritize and allocate resources to manage PSC risks in a comprehensive and structured manner. Thus, PSC management can concentrate on the main risks that lead to vulnerabilities inside the PSC. If the main risk can be tackled first, it will take less time and effort to mitigate the impacts of risks.

Third, it categorizes various risks into various groups of variables, Such as linkage, autonomous, dependent and independent. As a result of this classification, PSC managers can be better able to distinguish between different types of risks and how they are related to one another, develop mitigation strategies for independent risks, create backup plans for linkage risks, and keep an eye on dependent risks.

Furthermore, this classification can be utilized to explain, transfer, and communicate risk knowledge across various organizational departments and the PSC partners. Thus, it can enable efficient and effective management dealing with different risk categories from both the organization and the entire supply chain.

Conclusion and directions for future research:

Currently, academics and practitioners must have an in-depth understanding of the connections between various PSC risks. To achieve this goal and effectively address risks within the PSC, a comprehensive research approach was adopted.

This involved conducting a series of 13 in-depth semi-structured interviews with highly experienced practitioners in the PSC across three distinct provinces within Pakistan. Subsequently, a rigorous thematic analysis was carried out, leading to the identification of 20 distinct risk factors within the (PSC). To further refine and prioritize these risk factors, we employed the Delphi technique. This involved engaging a panel of ten experts specializing in relevant fields to validate and evaluate these risks. As a result of this collaborative effort, 16 of the most prominent and pertinent risk factors were carefully selected for focused consideration within the PSC context. Afterwards, we implemented the (TISM) methodology to unveil the possible interconnections and dependencies among the previously identified risk factors. Following this analysis, we utilized the fuzzy (MICMAC) approach to discern the pivotal risks within different categories. The findings of our study have revealed that risks associated with the pandemic and unstable political and economic conditions exhibit the highest driving power. Additionally, these risks occupy the lowest level within the TISM hierarchy. As such, these specific risks are accorded the utmost priority in the context of risk management and mitigation efforts.

Although this study has several limitations, it provides opportunities for future research in the following areas.

First, the empirical research was exclusively carried out within the borders of Pakistan. It is imperative to extend the application of the study findings to diverse countries to assess their broader applicability. Furthermore, conducting an international survey would yield valuable additional insights into the risks associated with (PSC) in various global contexts.

Second, no proactive measures have been suggested to address the risks under consideration. It is imperative to cultivate resilience capabilities and strategies within the (PSC) sector to effectively manage and mitigate these risks. This imperative arises from the shared necessity of all PSC companies to establish strategies for recovery in the face of potential risks.

Third, the impact of various (PSC) risks on one another has not yet been explored within the framework of TISM. We must integrate the

direction of influence, whether positive or negative when establishing the contextual relationships and interpreting them within the TISM methodology. When establishing a relationship between two elements, it becomes essential to explicitly specify the direction in which one element drives the other. To take relationship polarity into account in TISM (Sushil, 2018).

Last, exclusively qualitative research methodologies have been employed thus far; however, there is a compelling case for enhancing the analysis of (PSC) risks by embracing a hybrid approach that combines both qualitative and quantitative techniques in future investigations. As demonstrated by Hussein, (2009), the incorporation of both qualitative and quantitative methodologies when studying the same phenomenon yields tangible benefits, by using both qualitative and quantitative methods together, we can get more accurate and better understand the topic we are studying. Consequently, it is advisable to consider the potential utilization of structural equation modelling (SEM) in forthcoming research endeavors.

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Appendix 1: Transitivity Level Partition

Transitivity Level Partition 1

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	(RS&AS)	Levels	Match
R1	1,2,3,4,5,7	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2		FALSE
R2	1,2,3,4,5,7	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2		FALSE
R3	3	1,2,3,6,9,10,12,13,14,15,16	3	1	TRUE
R4	4	1,2,4,6,7,8,9,10,12,13,14,15,16	4	1	TRUE
R5	5	1,2,5,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	5	1	TRUE
R6	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,16	6,9,13,14,15	6		FALSE
R7	4,7	1,2,6,7,9,10,12,13,14,15,	7		FALSE
R8	4,8	6,8,9,13,14,15,16	8		FALSE
R9	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,16	9,13,15	9		FALSE
R10	1,2,3,4,5,7,10	6,9,10,12,13,14,15	10		FALSE
R11	11	6,9,11,13,14,15,16	11	1	TRUE
R12	1,2,3,4,5,7,10,12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,13,16	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12,13,14,16	14	14		FALSE
R15	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,15,16	15	15		FALSE
R16	3,4,8,11,16	6,9,13,14,15,16	16		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 2

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R1	1,2,7	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2		FALSE
R2	1,2,7	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2		FALSE
R6	1,2,6,7,8,10,16	6,9,13,14,15	6		FALSE
R7	7	1,2,6,7,9,10,12,13,14,15,	7	2	TRUE
R8	8	6,8,9,13,14,15,16	8	2	TRUE
R9	1,2,6,7,8,9,10,16	9,13,15	9		FALSE
R10	1,2,7,10	6,9,10,12,13,14,15	10		FALSE
R12	1,2,7,10,12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	1,2,6,7,8,9,10,13,16	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	1,2,6,7,8,10,12,13,14,16	14	14		FALSE
R15	1,2,6,7,8,9,10,12,13,15,16	15	15		FALSE
R16	8,16	6,9,13,14,15,16	16		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 3

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R1	1,2	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2	3	TRUE
R2	1,2	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,14,15	1,2	3	TRUE
R6	1,2,6,10,16	6,9,13,14,15	6		FALSE
R9	1,2,6,9,10,16	9,13,15	9		FALSE
R10	1,2,10	6,9,10,12,13,14,15	10		FALSE
R12	1,2,10,12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE

R13	1,2,6,9,10,13,16	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	1,2,6,10,12,13,14,16	14	14		FALSE
R15	1,2,6,9,10,12,13,15,16	15	15		FALSE
R16	16	6,9,13,14,15,16	16	3	TRUE

Transitivity Level Partition 4

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R6	6,10	6,9,13,14,15	6		FALSE
R9	6,9,10	9,13,15	9		FALSE
R10	10	6,9,10,12,13,14,15	10	4	TRUE
R12	10,12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	6,9,10,13	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	6,10,12,13,14	14	16		FALSE
R15	6,9,10,12,13,15	15	15		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 5

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R6	6	6,9,13,14,15	6	5	TRUE
R9	6,9	9,13,15	9		FALSE
R12	12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	6,9,13	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	6,11,12,13,14	14	14		FALSE
R15	6,9,12,13,15	15	15		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 6

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R9	9	9,13,15	9	6	TRUE
R12	12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	9,13	12,13,14,15	13		FALSE
R14	12,13,14	14	14		FALSE
R15	9,12,13,15	15	15		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 7

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R12	12,13	12,14,15	12		FALSE
R13	13	12,13,14,15	13	7	TRUE
R14	12,13,14	14	14		FALSE
R15	12,13,15	15	15		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 8

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R12	12	12,14,15	12	8	TRUE
R14	12,14	14	14		FALSE
R15	12,15	15	15		FALSE

Transitivity Level Partition 9

	Reachability Set (RS Row)	Antecedent Set (AS Column)	RS&AS	Level	Match
R14	14	14	14	9	TRUE
R15	15	15	15	9	TRUE

Appendix 2: Initial reachability matrix of PSC risks

	RI	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16
RI	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R2	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R6	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
R7	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R9	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
R10	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
R11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
R13	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1
R14	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0
R15	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0
R16	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

Appendix 3: Final reachability matrix of PSC risks

	RI	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16
RI	1	1	1 ^t	1 ^t	1 ^t	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R2	1	1	1	1 ^t	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R6	1	1	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1	1	1 ^t	0	1	1 ^t	0	0	0	0	1
R7	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R9	1 ^t	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1	1	1 ^t	1	1	1 ^t	0	0	0	0	1 ^t
R10	1	1	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	0	1 ^t	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
R11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
R12	1 ^t	0	1 ^t	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0				
R13	1 ^t	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1*	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1	1 ^t	0	1	0	0	1
R14	1 ^t	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1	1	1	0	1	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1	0	1 ^t
R15	1 ^t	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1	1*	1	1 ^t	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	1	1 ^t	0	1	1 ^t
R16	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1

Note: 1^t entries refer to transitivity relationships

Appendix 4: Binary direct reachability matrix of PSC risks

	RI	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16
RI	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R2	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R6	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
R7	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R9	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
R10	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
R13	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
R14	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
R15	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
R16	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0

Appendix 5: Fuzzy direct reachability matrix of PSC risks

	RI	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12	R13	R14	R15	R16
RI	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R2	0.9	0	0.7	0	0.7	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R6	0.5	0.3	0	0.7	0	0	0.5	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0.7
R7	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R8	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R9	0	0	0	0.9	0	0.7	0.9	0	0	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0
R10	0.7	0.5	0	0.9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
R12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0.3	0	0	0
R13	0	0	0	0.3	0	0	0	0	0.3	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
R14	0	0	0	0.7	0	0.3	0.3	0.7	0	0.7	0.7	0.9	0	0	0	0
R15	0	0	0	0.7	0.9	0	0.5	0	0	0.3	0	0.5	0	0	0	0
R16	0	0	0.7	0.3	0	0	0	0.7	0	0	0.5	0	0	0	0	0

Appendix 6: Empirical Evidence for Exploring PSC Risks

PSC first-order codes	PSC risks/themes	Second-order Cases from Pharmaceutical supply chain													Total dimensions		
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M			
There are businesses that, for various reasons, do not have bank accounts. This could be due to a lack of access to banking services in their area, financial constraints, or personal preferences...	Payment sluggishness	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			Financial risk

.... some hospitals may not pay us on time, which company will face financial issues. So, if one of them does not pay us, we will proceed with caution the next time we offer drugs to them.	Faulty debts		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
I think one of the major problems is inaccurate demand forecasting which affects our reputation and when customers can't find the products they want, they become dissatisfied and may turn to other companies that can meet their needs reliably...	Inaccurate demand forecasting	demand	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
...so we don't have proper contracts in place with our suppliers and we rely on oral contracts instead of written agreements which lead to a lack of clarity, and confusion and can result in delayed deliveries, subpar quality, or even supplier disputes.	Lack of contract management	contract	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
We must monitor and control the product quality and temperature at each stage of the production and transportation process, especially cool chain products...	Product Quality		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	Operation and Management risk.
...operating and maintaining complex machinery and equipment, qualified technicians and scientists are required. But the problem is that as time goes on, fewer skilled workers are available in this field, leaving only low-skilled workers.	Lack of skills		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
...mostly there is a lack of trust between the partners, they may be reluctant to disclose sensitive or crucial information and might fear that the information could be misused or used against them.	Lack of information visibility	information	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
There is no planning or discussion between the seller and buyer over how much they must create. The lack of definite strategies and procedures for demand forecasting is another concern.	Poor planning		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	Supply risk
One of the problems with supply and demand is that, on the one hand, we want to produce enough goods to satisfy demand. However, if we make too much, we run the risk of not being able to sell it all and building up surplus inventory.	Unbalanced supply and demand		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	
Another issue we are mostly facing is Counterfeit medicines which are	Counterfeit medicines		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	Demand risk

often sold at lower prices compared to genuine products.

Demand and supply can affect the market price of the product... consumers may seek alternatives to expensive branded drugs.

Fluctuation in price ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

We are facing all types of risks, intellectual property risk can disrupt the normal supply and demand of companies that invested time, money, and resources in developing the original medicine . . . may face a decline in sales, impacting their revenue and ability to invest in research and development of new drugs.

Intellectual property theft ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

Sui gas and electricity bills are the biggest expenses. Commercial energy units cost more per month than noncommercial ones...

High energy cost ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

The second risk is to compensate for warehouse expenses, companies might be forced to increase prices, which can result in decreased demand for their products.

Warehousing cost ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

Logistical & infrastructural risk

Sometimes rapid technological advancement has also required ongoing investment in infrastructure improvement and staff training to stay up with the evolving field.

Rapid technological advancement ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

The most important aspect to realize is that whenever there is a politically or economically unstable government, it affects the pharmaceutical industry.

Unstable political and economic conditions ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

. . . is another aspect that comes to mind is government policies. When the government impose tariffs or trade barriers on imported goods, it can disrupt the smooth flow of materials and products across borders.

Rapid changes in government policies ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

Geopolitical & Economical risk

We are also facing trade disputes which can disrupt supply chain flows by creating uncertainties and delays in transportation and customs processes and leading to longer lead times and potential shortages of medicines. . .

Trade disputes ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

In the previous year, we had a very big flood which caused severely disrupted transportation and logistics operations. Roads had become impassable due to floodwater, bridges had been

Weather condition ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

Environmental risk

damaged, and transportation infrastructure had been severely affected.

The pandemic impacted pharmaceutical systems, limiting access to essential medication facilities. The COVID-19 virus caused unheard-of shifts in demand for both new and old medications, while at the same time creating new uncertainties regarding their manufacturing, imports and distribution.

Global health crises (Pandemic) ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

